

LOGOPEDIC WORK WITH CHILDREN WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENT

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Abstract. This article provides information about speech therapy work with children with hearing loss.

Keywords: *weak, children, hearing, sound, difficulty, amplification, instruments, speech, perception, expressive, stuttering, tempo, impairment, rhinolalia, optical dysgraphia, dyslexia, dysarthria, mechanical, dyslalia, Galatia, aphasia, articulatory- acoustic.*

Logopedic influence can be effectively used in work with hearing-impaired children with partial hearing loss.

According to F.F. Rau, L.V. Neyman, and V.I. Beltyukov, "weak hearing is said to be such a decrease in hearing that there are difficulties in perceiving speech, but under specially created conditions (amplification of the voice, bringing the speaker close to the ear, using sound amplification devices) leash, etc.) it will be possible to engage in speech communication with the help of hearing.

It is accepted to refer to children who are hard of hearing as hearing-impaired, as opposed to deaf children (deaf children are unable to perceive speech even with the use of sound-amplifying devices). A clear and persistent decrease in hearing leads not only to speech perception but also to the impairment (or lack of development) of expressive speech. In this case, in each specific case, the level of expressive speech disorder (underdevelopment) depends on the degree of hearing

loss (the more severe the level, the worse it is), the time of onset of poor hearing, the conditions of the child's development (special measures for the development and preservation of speech application depends on its somewhat good condition.

For children with hearing loss, the lack of formation of speech components (components) directly related to hearing loss is typical. It covers all aspects of speech. However, in hearing-impaired people, there is also a form of speech impairment that is not related to the state of the hearing function. These are stuttering; speech tempo disorder, rhinolalia, optical dysgraphia and dyslexia, dysarthria, mechanical dyslalia, voice disorder, Galatia, and early childhood aphasia.

Phonetic-phonemic disorders.

The normal functioning of the phonemic system provides for the possibility of accurate auditory differentiation of all speech sounds (even when adding acoustically close sounds) and their correct pronunciation. These two sides, which characterize the state of the phonetic system, cannot be formed normally in early-onset hearing loss.

Children with hearing loss of the first degree can distinguish no more than 75% of consonants pronounced near the top of the ear in a normal conversational voice. At a distance of 0.5 m from the ear, consonant discrimination decreases to 60%, and at a distance of 2 m, the possibility of discrimination decreases even to 40%. occurs only because it relies on the whole image of words and phrases. In this case, the child understands the missing part of the word and phrase (most often he understands). If the child does not have perfect speech, such understanding will not be possible.

For the hard-of-hearing students of Part II, it is difficult to perceive the smooth and noisy sounds. In addition, pure acoustic properties indicate that these sounds began to differentiate relatively late in the tall salt. Here, the inhibitory effect of the speech movement analyzer on the speech hearing analyzer is

observed.

Distortion of sound pronunciation is common, especially among the hearing-impaired students of Part II. On top of that, not only consonants are broken, but also vowels. However, L.G. According to Paramonova, in the first section of the school for the hearing impaired, even in the upper grades, there are more cases of polymorphic disorders of sound pronunciation, as in the second section of the hearing impaired.

There are three main forms of speech impairment in hearing impaired:

In the absence of the sensor section of the speech apparatus, that is, in the incomplete functioning of the auditory analyzer, it is characteristic to replace one speech sound with another ("cherry" instead of "cherry", "hour" instead of "hour"). Distortion of sounds is somewhat less common than substitution of sounds. This is due to the lack of ability to clearly distinguish them from other sounds, or the complete lack of ability to hear them due to the partial reduction of the corresponding sound frequencies.

In the lower classes of the hearing-impaired class, such forms of sound pronunciation disorders are usually in the first place.

Due to the deficiency of the motor department of the speech apparatus, that is, defects in the structure or functioning of the articulation organs. The disorder is usually expressed by the incorrect pronunciation of sounds (sharp "s", etc.).

A mixed type of sound pronunciation disorder based on both sensory and motor deficits at the same time. In such children, the deficits in the pronunciation of some sounds in a child are related to the lack of ability to distinguish similar phonemes (s-z) by hearing, while the deficits in the pronunciation of other sounds are due to deficiencies in the structure or operation of the articulatory apparatus (for example, impaired pronunciation of the sound "r" due to the shortness of the tongue or "s" due to paralysis of the muscles of the tip of the tongue).

In many cases, the written speech of the hearing impaired reflects the

shortcomings of oral speech. We conditionally divide its violations into two main groups:

- 1) gross agrammatism is expressed in incorrect matching and use of auxiliaries, omission of the first and second level parts of the sentence, etc.;
- 2) presence of forms of dysgraphia associated with gross phonetic-phonemic underdevelopment (acoustic and articulatory-acoustic dysgraphia) present in the hearing impaired.

It is important to work with speech-impaired and hearing-impaired children on the correction of all impaired speech components, sound pronunciation, lexical-grammatical system, writing, and expressive speech.

The increase in the number of combined defects requires the improvement of their differential diagnosis and not only specific teaching methods but also speech therapy.

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